

Comparison of Topical Ketoconazole alone versus Topical Ketoconazole plus Topical Adapalene in the Treatment of Patients with Pityriasis Versicolor

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Abstract:

Background & Objectives: Pityriasis Versicolor (PV) is a chronic cutaneous fungal infection caused by *Malassezia* species. A recent study showed combination therapy consisting of Ketoconazole plus Adapalene gel to be superior to Ketoconazole monotherapy. The objective of this study was to compare the frequency of patients improved with Ketoconazole alone versus Ketoconazole plus Adapalene in the treatment of Pityriasis Versicolor.

Study design: Randomized controlled trial.

Place & duration of study: Department of Dermatology, CMH Lahore from 20th May 2016 to 19th November 2016.

Methods: This study included 80 patients, both male and female, aged between 18-70 yrs presenting with Pityriasis Versicolor. These patients were divided into two treatment groups. Randomly Patients in Group-A were given Ketoconazole cream alone while patients in Group-B were given combination therapy with Ketoconazole cream plus Adapalene gel applied separately with different timings. Outcome variable was number of patients improved after 2 weeks of treatment.

Results: The frequency of improvement at 2 weeks was significantly higher with the combination therapy (87.5% vs. 47.5%; $p=0.000$) as compared to Ketoconazole alone and this difference was significant across all age, gender and duration of disease groups.

Conclusion: The frequency of improvement was significantly higher with the combination therapy consisting of Ketoconazole plus Adapalene as compared to Ketoconazole alone, advocating preferred use of combination therapy in patients presenting with Pityriasis Versicolor in future practice.

Keywords: *Pityriasis Versicolor, Ketoconazole, Adapalene.*

INTRODUCTION

Pityriasis Versicolor is a chronic superficial fungal infection of upper layers of skin caused by lipophilic yeast (*Malassezia* species) that is present all over the world but is more common in tropical and subtropical regions.¹ It is seen in all age groups but is more common in young, post-puberty adults, owing to physiological changes in skin surface lipids during puberty.^{1,2} The current topical treatments include imidazole derivative like Clotrimazole, Ketoconazole, Miconazole and non-imidazole topical agents (Zinc Pyrithione etc). These topical drugs for Pityriasis Versicolor are usually safe except causing slight skin irritation or contact allergy rarely.³ There are few reports that Flutrimazole and Bifonazole preparations cause mild to moderate pruritus and burning. Selenium Sulfide is odourous and can produce skin dryness and irritation as compared to other available options.^{4,5} Whitfield ointment has also been reported to cause burning and irritation in multiple cases.⁶ Ketoconazole appears to be a safer topical treatment of choice in patients with this condition.⁷ In a recent study, Shi et al. (2015) reported that addition of Adapalene 0.1% gel to 2% Ketoconazole cream significantly increased the frequency of patients improved after 2 weeks of treatment (88% vs. 56%; $p=.0000$) as compared to 2% Ketoconazole cream monotherapy. Moreover, the combination therapy was

given once daily was more convenient to the patient as compared to monotherapy which was given twice daily.⁸ However, the above evidence is limited to only a single randomized controlled trial and there is lack of local studies. The Objective of our study is to repeat similar trial and confirm supremacy of combination therapy over monotherapy. Our results may provide an evidence for an improved therapeutic option for future patients with Pityriasis Versicolor.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was a randomized controlled trial carried out in the Department of Dermatology, CMH Lahore over a period of six months from May 2016 to 19th November 2016.

Non Probability, Consecutive Sampling technique was used. Sample size of 80 cases (40 in each group) was calculated with 80% power of test and 95% confidence level while taking expected frequency of patients improved at 2 weeks to be 88% with combination therapy and 56% with monotherapy.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients of both genders, aged between 18-70 years having Pityriasis Versicolor for ≤ 3 months

Exclusion criteria:

- Hypopigmented lesions (naked eye examination comparing the lesion to the normal surrounding skin); known Hypersensitivity to Adapalene gel or Ketoconazole cream ; use of systemic or topical anti-fungal agents in the preceding 3 months period; pregnant women or nursing mothers

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DATA COLLECTION

Sixty two patients presenting in the OPD of Dermatology Department at Combined Military Hospital, Lahore who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled into this study. Detailed history and written informed consent was obtained from each patient. These patients were divided into the following treatment groups randomly using lottery method. Patients in Group-A were advised to apply Ketoconazole 2% cream twice daily, while patients in Group- B were advised to apply combination treatment consisting of Ketoconazole 2% cream and Adapalene 0.1% gel once daily. Patients were followed after 2 weeks of treatment in outdoor and improvement was noted. Patient’s demographic details along with duration of disease and improvement on follow-up were noted in the attached proforma. All the examinations were performed by the same consultant dermatologist and all the microscopic examinations were done by the same Pathologist to eliminate bias.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 20. Numerical variables such as age and duration of disease were described as mean ±SD. Categorical variables like

gender and patients improved were presented by frequencies and percentages. Chi-square test was applied to compare frequency of patients improved between the two groups taking $p \leq 0.05$ as significant.

RESULTS

The age of the patients ranged from 18 years to 50 years with a mean of 29.55 ± 7.60 years. Majority of the patients were aged between 18-30 years ($n=52, 65.0\%$). There were 53 (66.3%) male and 27 (33.8%) female. The duration of disease ranged from 1 to 12 weeks with a mean of 6.54 ± 3.34 weeks as shown in Table 1. Statistically significant difference was not found between the two study groups in terms of age, gender and duration of disease as shown in Table 2. The frequency of improvement (complete resolution of scales on clinical examination and negative microscopic examination of skin scrapings after 2 weeks of treatment according to operational definition) was significantly higher with the combination therapy (87.5% vs. 47.5%; $p=0.005$) as compared to Ketoconazole alone and this difference was significant across all age, gender and duration of disease groups as shown in Table 3 and 4.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Sample

Age (years)	29.55±7.60
Age Groups	
18-30 years	52 (65.0%)
31-50 years	28 (35.0%)
Gender	
Male	53 (66.3%)
Female	27 (33.7%)
Duration of Disease (weeks)	6.54±3.34
<1 Month	26 (32.4%)
1-2 Months	27 (33.8%)
2-3 Months	27 (33.8%)

Table 2: Baseline Characteristics of Study Groups

Characteristics	Ketoconazole 2% cream alone n=40	Ketoconazole 2% cream + Adapalene 0.1% gel n=40	P value
Age (years)	29.95±7.67	29.15±7.60	0.641
Age Groups			
18-30 years	25 (62.5%)	27 (67.5%)	
31-50 years	15 (37.5%)	13 (32.5%)	0.639
Gender			
Male	27 (67.5%)	26 (65.0%)	
Female	13 (32.5%)	14 (35.0%)	0.813
Duration of Disease (weeks)	6.20±3.40	6.88±3.28	0.369
<1 Month	14 (35.0%)	12 (30.0%)	
1-2 Months	13 (32.5%)	14 (35.0%)	0.892
2-3 Months	13 (32.5%)	14 (35.0%)	

Independent sample t-test and chi-square test, observed difference was statistically insignificant

Table 3: Comparison of Improvement between the Study Groups

Improvement	Ketoconazole 2% cream alone n=40	Ketoconazole 2% cream + Adapalene 0.1% gel n=40	P value
Yes	19 (47.5%)	35 (87.5%)	0.005*
No	21 (52.5%)	5 (12.5%)	
Total	40	40	

Chi-square test, * observed difference was statistically significant

Table 2 : Stratification of Improvement between the Study Groups

Characteristics	Ketoconazole 2% cream alone n=40	Ketoconazole 2% cream + Adapalene 0.1% gel n=40	P value
Age Groups			
·18-30 years	12/25 (48.0%)	24/27 (88.9%)	0.001*
·31-50 years	7/15 (46.7%)	11/13 (84.6%)	0.037*
Gender			
·Male	13/27 (48.1%)	23/26 (88.5%)	0.002*
·Female	6/13 (46.2%)	12/14 (85.7%)	0.029*
Duration of Disease			
·<1 Month	7/14 (50.0%)	11/12 (91.7%)	0.022*
·1-2 Months	6/13 (46.2%)	12/14 (85.7%)	0.029*
·2-3 Months	6/13 (46.2%)	12/14 (85.7%)	0.029*

DISCUSSION

Ketoconazole seems to be a safer topical treatment of choice in patients with Pityriasis Versicolor and is widely practiced treatment option for such patients.⁷ A recent study showed that combination therapy consisting of Ketoconazole plus Adapalene gel was not only better than Ketoconazole monotherapy but also more convenient for the patient as well due to once daily regimen.⁸ However, the evidence was limited to only a single randomized controlled trial and there was no local published material available which necessitated the present study.

Our study compared the improvement with Ketoconazole alone versus Ketoconazole plus Adapalene in the treatment of Pityriasis Versicolor. This study involved patients of both genders aged between 18-70 years presenting with Pityriasis Versicolor. These patients were randomly divided into two treatment groups. Patients in Group-A received Ketoconazole cream alone while patients in Group-B received combination therapy with Ketoconazole cream plus Adapalene gel separately at different timings. Outcome variable was number of patients improved after 2 weeks of treatment. In our study, the age of the patients ranged from 18 years to 50 years with a mean of 29.55±7.60 years.

A similar mean age of 28.42 ±8.53 years has been reported previously by Moniriet al. among Irani patients

with Pityriasis Versicolor. Khan et al. in another local study reported mean age of 25.34±6.45 years among such patients at Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar.^{9,10} Wahid et al. reported much higher mean age of 51.3±9.4 years at Civil Hospital Karachi.¹¹ There were 53 (66.3%) male and 27 (33.8%) female patients in the study sample giving a male to female ratio of 2:1. A similar male predominance among patients of Pityriasis Versicolor has been reported by Haroon et al. (2:1) and Khan et al. (2.1:1).^{12,13} A much higher male predominance has been reported by Muzaffaret al. (5.5:1) and Khan et al. (4:1)[10,14] Wahid et al. reported much lower male predominance of 1.3:1.¹¹

The frequency of improvement at 2 weeks was significantly higher with the combination therapy (87.5% vs. 47.5%; p=0.000) as compared to Ketoconazole alone and this difference was significant across all age, gender and duration of disease groups. Our results are in conformity with the previously published report by Shi et al. who reported that addition of Adapalene 0.1% gel to 2% Ketoconazole cream significantly increased the frequency of patients improved after 2 weeks of treatment (88% vs. 56%; p=.0000) as compared to 2% Ketoconazole cream monotherapy.⁸ The present study is the first of its kind in local population and confirms the advantage of combination therapy over monotherapy. This new combination therapy has the advantage of once daily application which is more

convenient to the patient as compared to monotherapy which needs to be given twice daily. The strengths of the present study are strict exclusion criteria to control confounders and allocation of study groups by randomization to minimize bias. The results of the study were stratified to address effect modifiers.

The main limitation in our study was that we did not compare the two groups for side effects which is also an important aspect of management for which specific future study is recommended.

CONCLUSION

The frequency of improvement at 2 weeks was significantly greater with the combination therapy consisting of Ketoconazole plus Adapalene as compared to Ketoconazole alone advocating preferred use of combination therapy in patients presenting with Pityriasis Versicolor in future practice.

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